

Symbol of Contemporaneity: Bird in Whitman and Devkota

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Abstract:

The study of the symbols in American Romanticist Walt Whitman (1819-1892) and modern Nepali poet Laxmi Prasad Devkota (1909-1959) reveals that they hold subtle affinity in their use of bird to contemplate on the contemporary reality in their poem. Despite the variations in the time and place that both the poetic geniuses lived in, the close inspection of their poems shows proximity in treatment of specific symbols that discuss the formation of the present. This paper attempts to make a comparative analysis of Walt Whitman's "Out of the Cradle Endlessly Rocking" (1859) and Laxmi Prasad Devkota's "The Swallow and Devkota" in order to examine the use of bird as symbol. Whitman's bird and Devkota's Swallow merge into a singular symbol that signifies the eternal principles of life, creativity, and death. I content in this paper that both Whitman and Devkota employ bird in order to contemplate in the nature of present which appears vividly in the understanding of death for the former and birth for the latter.

The question of contemporaneity functions as a lens to scrutinize the perennially existing and troubling issues related to life, creativity, and death as such. Poetic imagination invents certain symbols to contemplate on the issues in order to delve into the core of the matter and bring about understanding for a specific time and society. Still, poetic speculations on such fundamental concepts of life and society show interface between poets in completely different cultures and society. However, this claim does not mean to overwrite any possibility of the latter poet studying the earlier poet. When American Romantic poet Walt Whitman (1819-1892) and modern Nepali poet Laxmi Prasad Devkota (1909-1959) are comparatively analyzed regarding their use of bird in their attempt to contemplate on the contemporary reality of their times, they tend to make use of bird as symbol of contemporaneity. In other words, both the bards employ [END PAGE 23] bird as a symbol to reflect on the nature of present in their respective societies. This study emphasizes on the ways both the poets work with three key concepts of life, creativity, and death in their poems. For the purpose of analysis, this study has taken Whitman's "Out of the Cradle Endlessly Rocking" and Devkota's "The Swallow and Devkota."

Walt Whitman treats bird as a part of organic unity in the chain of beings in the Nature. In "Out of the Cradle Endlessly Rocking", he projects American geography as an extension of cradle in that the title suggests that the poet derives extended pleasure of the childhood through American landscape as well. The dormant forces of the Nature help awaken the inner bard in young Whitman. Howard Nelson sums the poem that it is "an odd story of a boy who becomes fixated on a mockingbird and experiences a revelation from listening to its song" (497). By using the bird, the matured poetic voice in Whitman presents the ways in which the child in Whitman got acquainted to the principles of life. The making of full voice that represents the ethos of presence flows through the symbol of bird in the poem. Likewise, Laxmi Prasad Devkota's Swallow refers to the unification of the poet with the Nature. "The Swallow and

Devkota/Share the same nest and same trait" (1-2, 42-43, 61-62, and 78-79) appear as the refrain in this poem. These two lines reemphasize the notion that the Swallow as a symbol helps explore the inner composition of the poet himself. As a matter of fact, both Whitman and Devkota make use of bird as a poetic symbol in order to explore the inner content of their own self and to understand the nature of contemporary subjectivity.

As a symbol, the bird functions as an integral link of the chain in the organicity of the Nature. In the celebration of life, both Whitman and Devkota believe that the bird functions both as a means to explore the inner self and a way to project into the Nature their very selves. Whitman thinks that the memories of his childhood remain at the cornerstones of his personality when he addresses the bird as "sad brother" (9) while Devkota sings the song of creativity with the Swallow. Also, Mohan Lohani finds Devkota's poem a complex one in that it brings together human and the nature together through the contemplation on the nature of poetry through bird: as he argues, "The poet's persona is skillfully deployed to underscore the multi-**[END PAGE 24]** dimensional relationship between the human world and Nature as symbolized by the bird swallow" (3). Besides, Devkota's personal also accepts to have realized the origin of time and existence of present in the symphony that he sings together with the bird:

We sang the song of Gauri-Sankar,
The song that's duel of Prakriti and Purush.
The melodious creation of that beak and this taste-bud
Is our own abode.
The ages' children may open their eyes
Looking far ahead!
We sight constantly
The mud trodden by every feet,
That is the means of our abode. (46-54)

The genesis of creativity is rooted in the song that the poet sings together with the bird for Devkota. On the other hand, Whitman's bird sees that the past is the happiest of the time. The past represents the time of innocence, songs of joy, togetherness, and creativity for the 'he-bird' that loses his mate. Full of mourning, he sings songs of gloom and death whereby acquainting the young Whitman with the idea of death. The bird sings:

O past! O happy life! O songs of joy!
In the air, in the woods, over fields,
Loved! loved! loved! loved! loved!
But my mate no more, no more with me!
We two together no more. (125-129)

By listening to these words in the song of the bird, the young boy realizes the call of his soul to become a bard who can verbalize the problems of his day and weave a beautiful symphony out of the contradictions lying therein. For Whitman, the loss and the gain are perpetually lasting principles of life. As James Dougherty argues, "He likens human life to a play, in which the roles are forever fixed though the changing players may make more or less of their parts" (486). As a

matter of fact, Whitman contemplates on the nature of life through the bird and its song for the loss of its company. He symbolically dives deep into the nature of contemporary mundane reality in which things are repeating again and again, and inspiring to reveal the inner laws to the innocent boy in the world. **[END PAGE 25]**

The process of poetic creation synthesizes the two opposite polarities. Differently put, opposite forces come together so that creativity can be born in the real sense. Human presence in the room does not frighten the Swallow because Devkota and the Swallow are opposite forces like the tiger and the lamb. Also, Devkota notes: "Sitting down does Nature thread/ Both hearts in a string./It isn't afraid, I've no doubt!" (4-6). Spiritually and poetically connected, the bird and the bard unify the past and the present, and here and hereafter. On the other hand, the unity is personified in the young boy in Whitman. He thus sees the spiritual connection:

A man, yet by these tears a little boy again,
Throwing myself on the sand, confronting the waves,
I, chanter of pains and joys, uniter of here and hereafter,
Taking all hints to use them, but swiftly leaping beyond them,
A reminiscence sing. (18-22)

His memory of the bird revives a boy in the adult who chants both pains and joys and thus brings both the polarities of life together in order to draw music out of it. This synthesis of the opposite forces helps transform the young boy into a matured poet who encounters with his real essence and comes to identify his own voice. Now, the poet sees that he gets projected in the song of the bird that unites both the sky and the sea in the mind of the poet. As Whitman writes, "By the sea under the yellow and sagging moon,/The messenger there arous'd, the fire, the sweet hell within,/The unknown want, the destiny of me" (155-157). The perpetual impressions from the childhood encounters with the bird guide Whitman throughout his life in his quest for poetic creativity.

The symbol of bird haunts poetic minds in creative quest for poesy. As a phantom in the form of the bird, the creative drives get manifest in the mind of the poet. The bird as a symbol percolates into the psyche of the young observer and brings to the surface the flame of poetic contemplation on the nature of life and time as such. As a symbol for poetic creativity, Whitman's bird hisses the secret mantra of life which turns him into a bard. He observes:

The strange tears down the cheeks coursing,
The colloquy there, the trio, each uttering,
The undertone, the savage old mother incessantly crying, **[END PAGE 26]**
To the boy's soul's questions sullenly timing, some drown'd secret hissing,
To the outsetting bard. (139-143)

The Nature and the Muse work on his soul through his encounter with the mocking bird that loses his mate and sings to him at night. The inexperienced boy encounters the death as inseparable phenomenon of the nature for the first time in his life. The darkness and death together carry special significance in the text in that the former functions as the backdrop for the latter to show its magnitude in the psyche of the young observer. This night also symbolizes the

period of innocence in the poet's life. On top of it, Devkota's Swallow develops into a symbol for the Muse with whom the poet goes into the labor-pain. He pictures:

Flapping shall we reach the sea-shore
To turn back once
And to look through tears
At the forest of human beings.
Then shall we sink in the sea, the couple.
In happiness will then our souls submerge.
The labour-pain,
The anguish felt for this abode will vanish. (70-77)

For both poetic geniuses, the creative pain is symbolized through the use of bird. Whitman's bird presents death to the young boy and the event later turns into source for poetic inspiration, while Devkota sinks in the sea of poesy and his soul submerges in the bird's soul in a creative endeavor towards poetry. In this sense, the bird functions as a tool to poetically represent the process of creativity. Devkota works with the Swallow towards bringing about poetic creation, while Whitman employs of bird as a means to realize the pain of such process.

The bird refers to the source of poetic inspiration for both Whitman and Devkota. Whitman realizes his poetic power through its song that triggers his novice mindset, unaware about the nature of life as such. Later on, he gets confused whether the bird sings to search for its mate or to arouse poetic sensibility in him: this puzzle helps him realize the first rays of poetic light in his mind. The poetic sensibility begins to grow in the young boy when he begins to doubt whether the bird's lamentations are directed at the nature and loss or [END PAGE 27] the formation of the self of the future poet. In amazement, Whitman states:

For I, that was a child, my tongue's use sleeping, now I have heard you,
Now in a moment I know what I am for, I awake,
And already a thousand singers, a thousand songs, clearer, louder and more sorrowful
than yours,

A thousand warbling echoes have started to life within me, never to die. (146-149)
Heart full of music imparted through the song of the bird, poetic sensibility in Whitman is born because he passionately attempts to understand the song of the bird: "My own song awaked from that hour" (Whitman 178). In this way, the bird awakens the dormant poetic sensibility in the poet. After the disappearance of the 'she-bird', the trio unites 'he-bird,' 'the boy,' and 'the Nature' (Whitman 140) and also incorporates the observer (28-29) in Whitman into the Nature from which the birth of poesy takes place. The loss of 'she-bird' results in a situation where the tragedy gets transformed into the power of the muse: the he-bird begins to sing in search for his mate (71-129). Similarly, the Swallow becomes the ultimate symbol of human freedom that Devkota finds in the Nature. So, he says that he plans to fly those birds in the forest. The Swallow couple of poetry and poet become the symbol of celebration of life at present in that it provides nourishment to life in general. Devkota sings:

When the young ones hatched in the nest

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Grow their wings,
We in fondness wish
To take them to the forest to make them fly.
Then, will fly high
We the loving couple,
The swallow couple of poetry and poet. (63-69)

The bird symbolizes freedom derived from the poetic inspiration that takes deep flight into the realm of the Muse. From this point, the poet strategically presents the symbol to escape the mundane world in search of aesthetically sound world of poesy. Devkota's Swallow helps his poetic imagination soar high to seek for a world filled with bliss and ecstasy. Whitman and Devkota realize and express the [END PAGE 28] principles of creative life and quotidian world through the symbol of bird.

Both poets view birth and death through various acts associated with the bird from two poles of life in general. For Devkota, the generation of life appears to be more interesting as he emphasizes the nature of Purusha and Prakriti as the twin principles of life. On the other hand, Whitman chooses that the disintegration of human carries more significance in that his bird loses its mate while they plan to hatch the eggs. He says:

Two feather'd guests from Alabama, two together,
And their nest, and four light-green eggs spotted with brown,
And every day the he-bird to and fro near at hand,
And every day the she-bird crouch'd on her nest, silent, with bright eyes,
And every day I, a curious boy, never too close, never disturbing them,
Cautiously peering, absorbing, translating. (26-31)

The tragedy occurs after the 'she-bird' does not return one day. They never hatch the eggs. The tragic sense of life emerges intense in this instance as he presents the situation:

Till of a sudden,
May-be kill'd, unknown to her mate,
One forenoon the she-bird crouch'd not on the nest,
Nor return'd that afternoon, nor the next,
Nor ever appear'd again. (41-45)

The 'he-bird' laments for the loss of his mate until the young Whitman realizes the ultimate principle of life. The bird reveals the nature and arouses the poetic sense of the nature at the same time:

Lisp'd to me the low and delicious word death,
And again death, death, death, death,
Hissing melodious, neither like the bird nor like my arous'd child's heart,
But edging near as privately for me rustling at my feet,
Creeping thence steadily up to my ears and laving me softly all over,
Death, death, death, death, death. (168-173) [END PAGE 29]

Unlike Devkota's Swallow, Whitman's mocking bird helps reassert the Western sense of tragedy. For Devkota, the Swallow refers to a symbol for love, birth, and regeneration, while Whitman moves deep down into the Nature of life in order to mediate upon death through the use of bird as symbol.

Whitman employs the symbol of bird to contemplate on the making of his matured self by associating the mocking bird in Paumanok with the awakening of the poetic sensibility in him. The bird attracts the child in Whitman and acquaints him with the Nature by singing the song of death. The poet is disenchanted as he realizes that the bird sings for him. He sings: "Demon or bird! (said the boy's soul,)/ Is it indeed towards your mate you sing? Or is it really to me?" (144-145). The bard begins to gain a particular form within himself through the music of the bird which he thinks is really inspires the birth of creative mindset. The bird turns into a mentor for the bard as he says, "Listen'd to keep, to sing, now translating the notes,/Following you my brother" (69-70). The poem also pictures the development of poetic self in Whitman: Along with other poems like "Starting from Paumanok" and "As I Ebb'd with the Ocean of Life," "Out of the Cradle Endlessly Rocking" experiments with "dramatizing journey of selfhood" of the poet (Killingsworth 50). Presenting the first encounter with the nature and its principles perpetually dramatizing therein, the poet explores the inner nature of human through the exposure to the outside world. The inner contents of the bard are developed and shaped in a particular direction through the bird that turns into an effective instrument to sing the glory of American landscape as well.

Modern Nepali poet, Devkota employs the bird as a symbol to elucidate the process of poetic creation. Like Whitman, Devkota also sings the nation when he finds that "the melodious creation of that beak and this taste-bud is our own abode" (48-49). Spiritually one with the bird, the poet sings the glory of Gauri-Sankar, and Prakriti and Purush that symbolically refer to the genesis of creation as understood in the East. Devkota's Swallow embodies the vision of the philosophy of the Orient; similarly, Whitman's mocking bird awakens in the young boy his potential as a poet in future. In fact, both the poets present bird as an inherent symbolic value for the Muse. The flight of imagination and the swiftness of the bird are associated with **[END PAGE 30]** the creative process of poetry which both the poets see in their respective birds. Devkota plans to take the created into the contemporary society to soar high in the sky after the poetic process is fully realized in the creative domain through formation of self. In fact, the poet projects his inner landscape the depth of which takes him up in the sky and deep down to the source of poetic visualization of creative process as Ram Paudel contends that Devkota carefully establishes intimacy between himself and the bird (49). Thus, the bird becomes the ultimate symbol of human freedom that Devkota finds in the Nature. The bird becomes the symbol of celebration of life at present in that it provides nourishment to life in general.

Both Whitman and Devkota celebrate the creative principle of life and poetry through the use of bird that helps each of them to talk about life as the extension of creativity. The inner content of human subjectivity, life, and poetry reveal to each of them through the use of bird as a symbol in the form of abstractions like love, nation, death, and poetic voice. As a way of view

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the world at it appears to the subject at present, contemporaneity emerges as a perspective to view the spirit of the time at hand. In this regard, the symbol of the bird in each of the master poet turns into a powerful tool to reflect on the nature of time and reality of their respective societies. The poets treat bird a vehicle to realize the Nature of poetic process and quest for creative sensibility, along with the formation of the inner contents of their personalities. As a symbol, the bird soars high in the sky to realize the inner poetic voice in both the master poets.

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